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Review Article

A Review on FDA Approved Antiretroviral Drugs for the treatment of HIV

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ABSTRACT

HIV Medication help to provide lower viral load, fight infections, and improve the more precious quality of life. They can lower chances of spreading HIV. Aim to provide these medications are to control the growth of the virus, improve to functions of immune system works, as well as slow or stop symptoms. FDA enlisted list of medication for HIV time to time. This review help to know the method of treatment & selection of drug for the treatment of HIV infections.

INTRODUCTION

Antiretroviral drugs are medicines used to treat infections caused by retroviruses, especially HIV (Human Immunodeficiency Virus). They work by blocking different stages of the viral replication cycle, thereby reducing the amount of virus in the body (viral load), increasing CD4 cell count, and preventing progression to AIDS.

AIDS (acquired immunodeficiency syndrome)

Fig no. 1: AIDS symbol

AIDS is a life-threatening condition caused by the Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV).

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HIV attacks and weakens the body's immune system, especially CD4 (T-helper) cells, making it hard to fight infections and certain cancers.

If untreated, HIV infection gradually progresses to AIDS, the final stage of the disease.

•Symptoms

Symptoms vary depending on the stage:

1. **Early Stage** (Acute HIV Infection, 2–6 weeks after exposure):

- Fever
- Sore throat
- Rash
- Swollen lymph nodes
- Headache & body aches (flu-like illness)

Latent Stage (Clinical Latency, can last years):

Often no major symptoms Virus still multiplies slowly

2. **AIDS Stage** (Severe Immunodeficiency):

- Rapid weight loss
- Persistent fever and night sweats
- Chronic diarrhea
- Persistent cough / tuberculosis
- White patches in mouth (oral thrush)
- Skin rashes or unusual spots (Kaposi's sarcoma)
- Frequent infections (pneumonia, fungal, viral)

Method of treatment:

Each ART medicines restrict HIV at a various part of the Virus replication mode . For better knowledge about action of ART therapy must understand that how HIV infects the human cells & grows. Shortly like someone breaking into your house & reprogramming your security system so other to other introducer can get in.

During the condition HIV gets present inside your cells, writes instructions to makes copies of itself and uses your cells tools to form more copies of them. Not only it destroyed T-Cell during the processing as well preventing you from being able to fight some other infectious diseases.

Here also the specific steps involves with mechanisms:

• **Attachment**

HIV uses a protein GP120 to attach the receptor on our CD4 cells i.e. Immune cells. Receptors like locks HIV should began to enter the healthy cells. This is continuous step in which involves the changing of proteins shapes and locking on to more than one receptors.

• **Fusion**

The external coating of HIV join with the CD4 cell & this is called as Fusion.

• **Entry**

The capsid Of Virus: a shell made up of proteins carries its genetic material & tools it needs to replicate, get inside now.

• **Reverse transcription**

An enzyme HIV carries, makes DNA from RNAs and build the DNA from building blocks found inside your cells (nucleosides).

- **Integration**

HIV's DNA gets into the nucleus of the cell, where DNA lives. There are the enzymes integrated inserts the HIV DNA into your DNA. From it your cells read the virus's DNA as if they were your own body's instructions.

- **Transcription**

Your cell codes its DNA and HIV's DNA into messenger RNA (mRNA)s.

- **Translation**

The mRNA moves outside of the nucleus and uses your cell's ribosomes (similar to tiny factories that make proteins) to create proteins from its instructions. The mRNA moves outside of the nucleus and uses your cell's ribosomes to synthesized proteins from its instructions. Proteins are an important part of your body which play vital roles.

- **Assembly**

HIV proteases break these proteins apart and packages them into more viruses to infect other cells.

- **Budding and cell death**

The CD4 cell is destroyed when the viruses escape the cell to infect more cells.

Fig no. 2: mechanisms of HIV drugs

Antiretroviral Drugs : They do not cure HIV, but help patients live longer and healthier lives.

Classes of Antiretroviral Drugs: -

1. **Nucleoside/Nucleotide Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors (NRTIs)**

Block reverse transcriptase enzyme by mimicking DNA building blocks → prevents viral DNA formation.

Fig. no. 3: Antiretroviral drugs

- **Examples:** Zidovudine (AZT), Lamivudine (3TC), Tenofovir (TDF), Abacavir (ABC), Emtricitabine (FTC).

Treatment is called ART (Antiretroviral Therapy) or HAART (Highly Active Antiretroviral Therapy).

2. Non-Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors (NNRTIs)

Usually a combination of 3 drugs from at least 2 different classes.

Bind directly to reverse transcriptase and block its activity (different mechanism than NRTIs).

- **Example regimen:** Tenofovir + Lamivudine + Dolutegravir (TLD regimen) (commonly used worldwide).

- **Examples:** Efavirenz (EFV), Nevirapine (NVP), Etravirine, Rilpivirine.

Benefits of ART: -

3. Protease Inhibitors (PIs)

- Suppresses HIV replication.

Inhibit HIV protease enzyme → prevents virus from maturing and becoming infectious.

- Prevents progression to AIDS.

- **Examples:** Ritonavir (RTV), Lopinavir, Atazanavir, Darunavir, Indinavir.

- Improves quality of life and life expectancy.

- Reduces mother-to-child transmission and sexual transmission.

4. Integrase Strand Transfer Inhibitors (INSTIs)

Side Effects: - Nausea, diarrhea, headache.

Block integrase enzyme → stops viral DNA from inserting into host cell DNA.

Long-term: liver damage, kidney problems, lip dystrophy (fat distribution changes). Modern regimens have fewer and

- **Examples:** Raltegravir, Dolutegravir, Elvitegravir, Bictegravir.

Milder side effects: Extreme fatigue

5. Fusion Inhibitors

- **Treatment: -**

Prevent HIV from fusing with the host cell membrane → virus cannot enter CD4 cells.

There is no permanent cure for AIDS, but it can be controlled with treatment.

- **Example:** Enfuvirtide (T-20).

1) ART (Antiretroviral Therapy):

6. CCR5 Antagonists (Entry Inhibitors)

Combination of medicines that reduce the viral load, keep immune system stronger, and prevent progression to AIDS.

Block the CCR5 co-receptor on CD4 cells, stopping viral entry.

Life long treatment.

Example: Maraviroc.

1) Supportive Care:

Standard Treatment Approach

Preventing and treating opportunistic infections (antibiotics, antifungals, antivirals). Vaccinations (non-live vaccines where safe).

- HIV testing and early treatment.
- Preventing mother-to-child transmission during pregnancy.

Good nutrition and healthy lifestyle.

- Prevention: -
- Safe sex practices (condoms).
- Avoid sharing needles.

LIST OF FDA APPROVED ANTIRETROVIRAL DRUGS WITH THEIR BRAND NAME {Listed below are all FDA-approved HIV medications as of July 3, 2025}

Classes of Drugs	Name of Drugs
Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors (NRTIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abacavir (ABC; Ziagen) • Emtricitabine (FTC; Emtriva) • Lamivudine (3TC; Epivir) • Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF; Viread) • Tenofovir alafenamide (TAF; Vemlidy) • Zidovudine (AZT, ZDV; Retrovir)
Non-Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors (NNRTIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doravirine (DOR; Pifeltro) • Efavirenz (EFV; Sustiva*) • Etravirine (ETR; Intelence) • Nevirapine (NVP; Viramune*, ViramuneXR [extended release]*) • Rilpivirine (RPV; Edurant, Edurant PED*)
Integrase Strand Transfer Inhibitors (INSTIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cabotegravir (CAB; Apretude [injection]; Vocabria [tablet]) • Dolutegravir (DTG; Tivicay, Tivicay PD) • Raltegravir (RAL; Isentress, Isentress HD)
Protease Inhibitors (PIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atazanavir (ATV; Reyataz) • Darunavir (DRV; Prezista) • Fosamprenavir (FPV; Lexiva*) • Ritonavir (RTV; Norvir) • Tipranavir (TPV; Aptivus)
Fusion Inhibitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enfuvirtide (T-20; Fuzeon*)
CCR5 Antagonist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maraviroc (MVC; Selzentry)
Attachment Inhibitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostemsavir (FTR; Rukobia)
Post-Attachment Inhibitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ibalizumab-uiyk (IBA; Trogarzo)
Capsid Inhibitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lenacapavir (LEN; Sunlenca [for treatment], Yeztugo [for prevention])
Pharmacokinetic Enhancer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cobicistat (COBI; Tybost)
Combination HIV Medications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abacavir/lamivudine (ABC/3TC; Epzicom*) • Abacavir/dolutegravir/lamivudine (ABC/DTG/3TC; Triumeq, Triumeq PD) • Abacavir/lamivudine/zidovudine (ABC/3TC/ZDV; Trizivir*) • Atazanavir/cobicistat (ATV/COBI; Evotaz) • Bictegravir/emtricitabine/tenofovir alafenamide (BIC/FTC/TAF; Biktarvy) • Cabotegravir/rilpivirine (CAB/RPV; Cabenuva) • Darunavir/cobicistat (DRV/COBI; Prezcobix)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Darunavir/cobicistat/emtricitabine/tenofovir alafenamide (DRV/COBI/FTC/TAF; Symtuza) • Dolutegravir/lamivudine (DTG/3TC; Dovato) • Dolutegravir/rilpivirine (DTG/RPV; Juluca) • Doravirine/lamivudine/tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (DOR/3TC/TDF; Delstrigo) • Efavirenz/emtricitabine/tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (EFV/FTC/TDF; Atripla*) • Efavirenz/lamivudine/tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (EFV/3TC/TDF; Symfi, Symfi Lo*) • Elvitegravir/cobicistat/emtricitabine/tenofovir alafenamide (EVG/COBI/FTC/TAF; Genvoya) • Elvitegravir/cobicistat/emtricitabine/tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (EVG/COBI/FTC/TDF; Stribild) • Emtricitabine/rilpivirine/tenofovir alafenamide (FTC/RPV/TAF; Odefsy) • Emtricitabine/rilpivirine/tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (FTC/RPV/TDF; Complera) • Emtricitabine/tenofovir alafenamide (FTC/TAF; Descovy) • Emtricitabine/tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (FTC/TDF; Truvada) • Lamivudine/tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (3TC/TDF; Cimduo) • Lamivudine/zidovudine (3TC/ZDV; Combivir*) • Lopinavir/ritonavir (LPV/r; Kaletra)
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